

SYNTHETIC INVESTIGATIONS IN THE HYDROXY-COUMARIN SERIES.
PART I. A GENERAL METHOD FOR THE SYNTHESSES OF
4-HYDROXYCOUMARINS

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A general method for the synthesis of 4-hydroxycoumarins has been described.

After the identification by Link *et al.* (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1924 138, 21, 513, 529; 1928, 152, 941) of 3:3'-methylene-bis (4-hydroxycoumarin) (I) as the active agent causing haemorrhage of the cattle, fed on spoiled sweet clover hay and the discovery of the general anticoagulant properties of 3-alkyl-4-hydroxycoumarins, these compounds are looked upon as potent drugs in cases of thrombosis. As such, attempts (Link *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 2285, 2288, 2292; 1944, 66, 656, 900, 906) are being made to investigate their chemistry and also the synthetic routes by which these compounds can be prepared.

In the following lines, has been described, a method for the synthesis of 3-methyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (II, R=Me) which offers possibilities of syntheses of other similar (R=an alkyl radical) compounds.

Acetylsalicylic acid is condensed through its acid chloride in the cold with the sodio-salt of methyl malonic ester. The resulting acetylsalicyl-methylmalonic ester is hydrolysed with very dilute sulphuric acid ($p_n=1$) by refluxing for 6 hours. On cooling, crystals of 3-methyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (II, R=Me) separate: these on recrystallisation from dilute alcohol melt at 226-27° (Lit. m.p. 227-28°, Satahman, Wolff and Link, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 2285).

The very mild hydrolysing agent like dilute sulphuric acid of $p_n 1$ has been tried purposely as we wish to utilise these conditions for synthesis of compounds containing sensitive radicals in the 3 position of the coumarin ring.

EXPERIMENTAL

Acetylsalicylic acid was prepared by the following method (*cf.* Kaufmann, *Ber.* 1909, 42, 3482).

A mixture of salicylic acid (30 g.), acetic anhydride (50 g.), dry benzene (600 c. c.) and a few drops of pyridine was refluxed for 3 hours in a flask fitted with a condenser and

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a guard tube. 400 C. c. of benzene were distilled off and the residue in the flask was allowed to crystallise overnight. The crystals were filtered and washed with benzene and dried, m.p. 128°. On repeated crystallisations from benzene, it melted at 133°, yield 40 g.

Acetylsalicyl Chloride.—Acetylsalicylic acid (10 g.) was converted to its acid chloride, (b. p. 135°/12 mm.) by the usual thionyl chloride (6 c. c.) method, yield 8.4 g.

Ethyl Acetylsalicyl-methylmalonate.—Methylmalonic ester (8 g., prepared by condensing ethyl propionate with oxalate, followed by pyrolysis) was dropped on to 1.1 g. of molecularised sodium in dry benzene in the cold and kept overnight to form the sodio-salt. Acetylsalicyl chloride (8.4 g.) was then added in the cold with shaking when the reaction mass set as a jelly and kept as such for 6 hours and then refluxed on a water-bath for 2 hours. On cooling, it was diluted with excess of cold water, extracted with benzene, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water, and benzene was removed. The residue in the flask was distilled and the fraction boiling at 198°/4 mm. was collected, yield 5 g. (Found: C, 60.9; H, 5.96. $H_{17}C_{20}O_4$, requires C, 60.7; H, 5.95 per cent).

3-Methyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (II, R = Me).—Ethyl acetyl salicyl-methylmalonate (4 g.) was refluxed with dilute sulphuric acid (p_H 1, 40 c. c.) for 8 hours. After cooling, white crystals separated which were filtered off and dried on a porous plate to remove any adhering oil. On recrystallisation from dilute alcohol, it melted at 226-27°. (Found: C, 68.2; H, 4.53. $C_{11}H_8O_3$, requires C, 68.2; H, 4.54 per cent).

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